

CYANOCAMPHORANILIC ACIDS AND THEIR ROTATORY POWERS.

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3'- and 4'-cyanocamphoranilic acids have been prepared and their rotatory powers determined. The position of CN group in the sequence of substituent groups is anomalous. It should be in the proximity of COOH group, but actually it falls with the halogens.

Rule and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1121 *et seq.*), have shown that the polar effect of a substituent group is manifest in optical activity. The order in which the substituents are arranged is identical with the order obtained from the dipole moment. This series such as NO₂, COOH, CN, Halogens, H, Me, NMe₂, which is deduced from the dipole moments, represents a gradual transition from strongly electronegative groups through hydrogen to those increasingly electropositive in character.

In previous papers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1967; 1927, 1996 *et seq.*), the following values were obtained for 4'-camphoranilic acids in methyl alcohol.

	COOH.	C ₂ H ₅ .	Cl.	OEt.	Me.	OMe.	Br.	i.
[α] _D	255	59.0	58.8	56.3	56	53.3	51.3	44.16

We should expect that substitution of CN group in camphoranilic acid will increase the rotation of the parent compound. 4'-Cyanocamphoranilic acid, now prepared, has [α]_D, 58.0 (methyl alcohol). The position of this group is, therefore, anomalous in the sequence of substituent groups; it should be in the proximity of COOH group.

3'-Cyanocamphoranilic acid, as expected, has smaller rotatory power than the corresponding 4'-isomeride in all the solvents tried.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Camphoric anhydride and cyanoaniline in molecular proportions were heated with a little fused sodium acetate for 3 to 4 hours in an oil-bath at 120-30° and the product extracted with alcohol. At a slightly higher temperature the yield diminished.

4'-Cyanocamphoranilic acid was extracted with alcohol (animal charcoal), and precipitated by the addition of water and crystallised from dilute

alcohol as a yellowish powder, m.p. 140° . (Found : N, 8.97 ; Equiv., 304. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.3 per cent. Equiv., 300).

3'-Cyanocamphoranilic acid, isolated in a similar way, was extracted with a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide or ammonium hydroxide and the product reprecipitated by the addition of dilute acetic acid or hydrochloric acid, the process being repeated till the m.p. rose to $108-10^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 8.5, 8.7 ; Equiv., 318. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires N, 8.8 per cent. Equiv., 318).

Rotations of Cyanocamphoranilic Acids.

[The readings were taken in 2 dcm. tube.]

Solvent.	Conc. g./25 c.c.	α_D .	$[\alpha]_D$.	Conc. g./25 c.c.	α_D	$[\alpha]_D$
	3'-Cyanocamphoranilic acid.			4'-Cyanocamphoranilic acid.		
MeOH	0.20 g.	0.79°	48.1°	0.25°	1.16°	58.0
EtOH	0.20	0.62	38.8	0.25	1.03	51.5
Me ₂ CO	0.20	0.60	37.5	0.25	0.99	49.5
MeEtCO	0.20	0.47	29.3	0.25	0.80	40.4

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